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Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AND ITS
SEVERITY GRADES AMONG CIRRHOTIC PATIENTS DUE TO
HEPATITIS C****¹-Dr.Kiran Yasmeen Malik, ²- Dr.Shahrukh Javaid Warraich , ³-Dr.Mehar Jamil**¹ Punjab Medical College Faisalabad² Foundation university Medical college Islamabad³ Foundation University Medical college Islamabad**Abstract:**

Objective: To the determination of the frequency of vitamin D deficiency and intensity grades among cirrhotic patients due to hepatitis C.

Study Design: Descriptive / cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study: The study was conducted at Medicine Department of Allied Hospital Faisalabad from March 2017 to December 2017

Materials and Methods: The total number of patients in this study were 210 who were observed carefully. Patients with history of primary hyperparathyroidism, osteomalacia and bone metastatic diseases and patients on drugs such as vitamin D replacement therapy, thiazide diuretics, phenytoin, Antacids and glucocorticoids were excluded. They were admitted in Medical Department Of Allied Hospital Faisalabad for further evaluation. Blood was obtained for detection of serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25OHD) deficiency and once detected was put in different categories as mild, moderate and severe.

Results: The mean age in the study was 50 years with standard deviation ± 1.33 . 58% patients were male, forty two patients were female. The deficiency of vitamin D was found in 92% patients.

Conclusion: We conclude that the frequency of vitamin D deficiency was found in 92% patients who were diagnosed with hepatitis C.

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INTRODUCTION:

A scarring of the liver that is called cirrhosis leads to the formation of fibrous (scar) tissue. This will lead to derangement of the liver functions in a progressive fashion as a consequence. Any long standing injury to the liver can result in cirrhosis. A vital role is played by the liver in the metabolism of vitamin D as Vitamin D₃ is hydroxylated by hepatic 25 hydroxylase for its conversion into 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃. The liver's functions are affected in cirrhosis, this may result in disturbance of the hydroxylation step of vitamin D metabolism leading to deficiency of vitamin D. In calcium and phosphorus homeostasis and promoting bone mineralization Vitamin D is important [1]. Vitamin D₃ deficiency is significantly recognized in chronic liver disease and cirrhotic patients [2,3], According to one study published in the United States, up to 92% chronic liver disease and cirrhotic patients have some degree of vitamin D deficiency [4]. In the hepatitis C cirrhosis group, 16.3% (7/43) had mild, 48.8% (21/43) had moderate, and 30.2% (13/43) had severe vitamin D deficiency [4]. It is now proved by one study that vitamin D deficiency is related to the degree of liver dysfunction rather than etiology [5]. One study conducted on HCV-HIV co-infected patients shows that low serum 25(OH) D₃ correlates with the severity of liver fibrosis rather virological response to therapy or severity of immunodeficiency [3]. Low vitamin D is linked with severe fibrosis and low sustained virological response (SVR) in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C patients [6].

Vitamin D deficiency is implicated in the pathogenesis of Osteopenia and Osteoporosis. A study about frequencies of Osteoporosis in cirrhotic patients shows that it is due to Hepatitis B and C [7]. It shows that Osteoporosis was evident in 26% subjects and Osteopenia was present in 42% patients and 32% of subjects had BMD normal.

The deficiency of vitamin D is identified in chronic liver disease and cirrhosis, this study establishes burden of severity of vitamin D deficiency cirrhotic patients due to hepatitis C in our set of population and the result of the study can be used to recommend future guidelines for planning.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study was undertaken at the Department Of Medicine Allied Hospital faislabad. The study has a descriptive design and is cross-sectional.

The subjects with liver cirrhosis male as well as female subjects above the age of 20 years were included in the study. The patients who have systemic diseases which can be influential in vitamin D levels also patients who had history of primary hyperparathyroidism, osteomalacia, malignancy/bone metastatic diseases, also the patients who are on drugs like vitamin D replacement therapy, were not included.

RESULTS:

The age of the subjects and percentage was 4(2%) < 30 years, 21(10%) 31-40 years, 88(42%) between 41-50 years, 70(33%) patients between 51-60 years and 27(13%) patients were above 60 years. Mean age remains as 50 ± 1.33 years. 122(58%) male, 88(42%) female. Vitamin D levels was normal 17(8%), low in 193(92%) patients, vitamin D deficiency in 193(92%) patients, Severe vitamin D deficiency among 48(25%) patients, 97(50%) patients with moderately deficient and 48(25%) severe deficiency (Table No.1).

Association of severity of vitamin D deficiency among age distribution was analysed as among 193 cases of vitamin D deficiency 48 patients had mild deficiency of vitamin D, in which 4 patients among 31-40 years, 19 patients ranged 41-50 years, 18 between 51-60 years and 7 patients more than 60 years. Among 97 patients moderate deficiency of vitamin D was found, 8 patients of 31-40 years, 42 between 41-50 years, 35 ranged 51-60 years and 12 more than 60 years. Severe deficiency of vitamin D was found in 48 patients, of which 3 between 31-40 years, 19 between 41-50 years, 18 patients 51-60 years and 8 more than 60 years. (Table No 2).

Vitamin D deficiency among genders 193 cases of vitamin D deficiency. 48 patients had mild deficiency, 27 male and 21 female. 97 with moderate deficiency, 60 male and 37 female. 48 with severe deficiency of vitamin D, 23 were male and 25 female (Table No 3).

Table No.1. Demographic variable of patients

Variable	No. Patients	Percentage
Age Distribution		
• < 30 years	4	2%
• 31-40 years	21	10%
• 41-50 years	88	42%
• 51-60 years	70	33%
• > 60 years	27	13%
Gender Distribution		
• Male	122	58%
• Female	88	42%
Vitamin D Level		
• Normal	17	8%
• Low vit. D Level	193	92%
Vitamin D Deficiency		
• Yes	193	92%
• No	17	8%
Severity Of Vitamin D Deficiency		
• Mild	48	25%
• Moderate	97	50%
• Severe	48	25%

Table No. 2. Association of severity of vitamin d deficiency in age distribution (n=193)

Severity /Age	31-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years	>60 years	Total
Mild	4	19	18	7	48
Moderate	8	42	35	12	97
Severe	3	19	18	8	48
Total	15	80	71	27	193

Chi square test was applied in which P value was 0.591

Table No. 3. Association of severity of vitamin d deficiency in gender distribution (n=193)

Severity /Gender	Male	Female	Total
Mild	27	21	48
Moderate	60	37	97
Severe	23	25	48

DISCUSSION:

Cirrhosis occurs due to a long-standing injury to the liver. Liver plays a vital role in the metabolism of vitamin D as Vitamin D3 is hydroxylated by hepatic 25 hydroxylase to convert it into 25-hydroxyvitamin D3. Cirrhosis results in disturbance in the hydroxylation of vitamin D metabolism leads to vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency is common (92%) among the patients with chronic liver disease, with at least one third of them suffering from vitamin deficiency D. This study finds that deficiency of vitamin D is evident in 92% of patients. 193(92%) patients of which 48(25%) mild deficiency of vitamin D, 97(50%) moderate deficiency and 48(25%) severe deficiency. Another study conducted by Arteh J et al [8] which had 109 patients in 118 (92.4%) had somewhat vitamin D deficiency. Severe vitamin D deficiency (<7 ng/ml) was common among patients who had cirrhosis as compared to non-cirrhotic (29.5% versus 14.1%, P value = 0.05). Female, African American, and cirrhosis were independent predictors of severe vitamin D deficiency in chronic liver disease.

A lower serum 25 (OH) D level was previously reported in different populations in terms of the cause and severity of chronic liver disease [9,10], We confirmed the reduction of 25 (OH) D to a homogeneous cohort for patients with G1 CHC, with low prevalence of Fibrosis F4. Although the significant trend in 25 (OH) D was found to be reduced with increased fibrosis levels, the subgroup of patients with light fibrosis (F1) also observed a significant reduction and it is unlikely that low levels of 25 (OH) D completely explained by decreased liver function.

Our study shows that a low level of 25 (OH) D is involved regardless of the gender of women and the intensity of necroinflammatory activity. Although the study did not confirm the correlation between the female sex and the lower level of 25 (OH) D, due to the decrease observed in women over 55 years, but not in men of the same age group, and due to the significant interaction between gender and age, we can imagine that hormonal changes in women after birth can modify the vitamin D status [11,12]. Our results highlight the inverse relationship between 25 (OH) D and the intensity of necroinflammatory activity. The lack of this relationship can be attributed to differences in middle age, alcohol consumption and the incidence of obesity and diabetes. In any case, we have declared a significant effect of metabolic changes on severe fibrosis of ferritin, a distance marker and metabolic syndrome [13].

It is possible that a reduced level of 25 (OH) D may promote the promotion of fibrosis itself. Different models give way to evidence that vitamin D, interacting with vitamin D receptor, protects oxidative stress [14] and it can influence the proliferation as well as gene expression of fibroblasts [15,16], also reduces the fibrogenic activity of liver stellate cells [17,18]. However, further studies may establish a link between vitamin D deficiency and fibrosis in patients with CHC. This study gives evidence that serum 25 (OH) D levels have a negative independent risk factor for SVR. This observation may also be needed in many different cohorts of patients to call it a medical evidence, but in this study it is supported by Data, that it contributes to the role of vitamin D in modifying the immune response [17,18], a recent clinical data [19] reporting higher early virological response rate in CHC treated with standard of care plus vitamin D as compared to standard care only.

Finally, the data from the literature suggests, that steatosis [18] and low cholesterol levels, a known surrogate marker of fibrosis severity[13], are associated with lower SVR rate. Any association between IR and SVR was not found.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that the frequency of vitamin D deficiency was evident in 92% patients.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest that has to be declared by any author.

REFERENCES:

1. Holick MF. Vitamin D deficiency. *N Engl J Med* 2007; 357(3):266-81.
2. Lim LY, Chalasani N .Vitamin D Deficiency in Patients with Chronic Liver Disease and Cirrhosis. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep* 2011; 14(1):67-73.
3. Terrier B, Carrat F, Geri G, Pol S, Piroth L, Halfon P, et al. Low 25-OH vitamin D serum levels correlate with severe fibrosis in HIV-HCV co- infected patients with chronic hepatitis. *J Hepatol* 2011; 55(4):756-61.
4. Arteh J, Narra S, Nair S. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in chronic liver disease. Department of Internal Medicine, University of Tennessee Health Science Center, Memphis, TN 38163, USA, *Dig Dis Sci* 2010;55(9):2624-8.
5. Mikkil M, Søren PJ, Peter O, Jørgen A, Hendrik V, Mette B, et al. Vitamin D deficiency

- in cirrhosis relates to liver dysfunction rather than aetiology, *World J Gastroenterol* 2011; 17(7):922–925.
6. Petta S, Cammà C, Scazzone C, Tripodo C, Di Marco V, Bono A, et al. Low vitamin D serum level is related to severe fibrosis and low responsiveness to interferon-based therapy in genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C. *Hepatology* 2010; 51(4):1158–67.
 7. Mohammad J, Arif S, Ijaz MK, Khalid H, Sher R, Abbas KK, Iqbal A, Shabir AK. Frequency of osteoporosis in patients with cirrhosis due to hepatitis B and hepatitis C: a study of 100 cases. *J Ayub Med Coll* 2009; 21(3):51–3.
 8. Arteh J, Narra S, Nair S. Prevalence of Vitamin D Deficiency in Chronic Liver Disease. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences* 2010;55(9): 2624–8.
 9. Monegal A, Navata M, Guanabens N, Peris P, Pons F, Martinez de Osaba MJ, et al. Osteoporosis and bone mineral metabolism disorders in cirrhotic patients referred for orthotopic liver transplantation. *Calcif Tissue Int* 1997; 60:148–54.
 10. Targher G, Bertolini L, Scala L, Cigolini M, Zenari L, Falezza G, et al. Associations between serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D3 concentrations and liver histology in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis* 2007;17: 517–4. Petta S, Camma C, Di Marco V, Alessi N, Cabibi D, Caldarella R, et al. Insulin resistance and diabetes increase fibrosis in the liver of patients with genotype 1 HCV infection. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2008; 103:1136–44.
 11. Moucari R, Asselah T, Cazals-Hatem D, Voitot H, Boyer N, Ripault MP, et al. Insulin resistance in chronic hepatitis C: association with genotypes 1 and 4, serum HCV RNA level, and liver fibrosis. *Gastroenterol* 2008;134:416–23.
 12. Vari IS, Balkau B, Kettaneh A, André P, Tichet J, Fumeron F, et al. DESIR Study Group. Ferritin and transferrin are associated with metabolic syndrome abnormalities and their change over time in a general population: Data from an Epidemiological Study on the Insulin Resistance Syndrome (DESIR). *Diabetes Care* 2007;30:1795–801.
 13. Veldman C, Cantorna M, DeLuca H. Expression of 1, 25 dihydroxyvitamin D3 receptor in the immune system. *Arch BiochemBiophys* 2000;374:334–8.
 14. Willheim M, Thien R, Schratlbauer K, Bajna E, Holub M, Gruber R, et al. Regulatory effects of 1 α , 25 dihydroxyvitamin D3 on the cytokine production of human peripheral blood lymphocytes. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1999;84: 3739–44.
 15. Timms PM, Mannan N, Hitman GA, Noonan K, Mills PG, Syndercombe-Court D, et al. Circulating MMP9, vitamin D and variation in the TIMP-1 response with VDR genotype: mechanisms for inflammatory damage in chronic disorders? *Q J Med* 2002;95:787–96.
 16. Cigolini M, Iagulli MP, Miconi V, Galiotto M, Lombardi S, Targher G. Serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D3 concentrations and prevalence of cardiovascular disease among type 2 diabetic patients. *Diabetes Care* 2006;29:722–4.
 17. Cantorna MT, Zhu Y, Froicu M, Wittke A. Vitamin D status, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3, and the immune system. *Am J Clin Nutr* 2004; 80(Suppl):1717S–20S.
 18. Abu-Mouch S, Fireman Z, Jarchovsky J, Assy N. The beneficial effect of vitamin D combined eg interferon and ribavirin for chronic HCV infection. *Hepatology* 2009;50(Suppl.):LB20.
 19. Camma C, Bruno S, Di Marco V, Di Bona D, Rumi M, Vinci M, et al. Insulin resistance is associated with steatosis in nondiabetic patients with genotype 1 chronic hepatitis C. *Hepatology* 2006;43:64–71.
 20. Cammà C, Petta S. Insulin resistance in HCV mono-infected and in HIV/HCV co-infected patients: looking to the future. *J Hepatol* 2009;50: 648–51.